

Predicting Self-Shielded Multigroup Microscopic Cross Sections Using Artificial Neural Networks

Joshua Nichols¹, Ben Whewell², Nathan Gibson², Andrew Osborne^{1*}

¹Colorado School of Mines, 1012 14th St., Golden, CO

²Los Alamos National Laboratory, Los Alamos, NM

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803742

ABSTRACT

Multigroup neutron transport models are used widely in simulation codes due to their memory and compute efficiency compared to continuous energy methods. However, multigroup codes rely on nuclear data prepared using approximate methods that require significant manual effort and expertise to account for self-shielding effects. In addition, multigroup nuclear data libraries prepared in this way can be limited in their applicability for modeling diverse reactors and operating conditions. Here we show that trained artificial neural networks can predict self-shielded microscopic cross sections accurately in fixed pincell simulations containing uranium dioxide fuel. The model's predictive accuracy remains high across fuel enrichment and burnup ranges encountered in light water reactors. Critically, the neural networks' predictions require only the atomic concentration of the fuel's constituent nuclides as inputs. The networks are trained using 8,500 samples of training data generated using continuous energy OpenMC pincell simulations. The trained neural networks predict self-shielded total, fission, absorption, elastic, and total scattering cross sections for combinations of 90 nuclides in the CASMO-8 energy group structure. The neural networks' predictions of self-shielded cross sections are validated by comparison with 1,500 samples of reference cross sections unseen during training and tallied using OpenMC simulations. The predicted and ground truth cross sections in the validation data set agree to within 0.152% on average.

Keywords: Self-Shielding, Artificial Neural Networks, Reactor Physics, Monte Carlo Simulation, Machine Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Multigroup models solve neutron transport equations by discretizing the energy domain into a grid consisting of two or more groups. Simulation codes implementing multigroup methods require nuclear data that are tabulated on the same energy grid. While the preparation of macroscopic multigroup nuclear cross is straightforward when using continuous energy Monte Carlo codes, these data have limited applicability. This is because macroscopic cross sections depend on both materials' atomic concentrations and the neutron flux, both of which evolve over time in an operating reactor and differ significantly between reactor types. Although microscopic cross sections can be tabulated instead, and used to calculate macroscopic data at runtime, preparation of microscopic data requires significantly more effort. The main difficulty in preparing accurate microscopic multigroup cross sections arises due to self-shielding. This phenomenon is characterized by a reduction in the effective cross sections of a nuclide when it is present at high concentrations. Self-shielding is particularly acute in the resonance region where large, sharp neutron absorption resonances cause the flux profile to reduce accordingly. Because the energy resolution of multigroup data is typically too coarse to resolve the effect of these resonances on the neutron flux, approximate methods are typically used to tabulate microscopic cross sections at various levels of self-shielding.

A variety of approximations have been developed to prepare accurate microscopic multigroup cross sections. Traditional methods for generating self-shielded cross sections range from interpolation schemes like Bondarenko and Tone's method [1,2], to integration-based techniques like the subgroup

*osbornea@mines.edu

method [3]. Since their introduction, these methods have undergone incremental refinements that have significantly improved their applicability and accuracy [4,5]. Nuclear data processing codes such as NJOY [6] have also been available for decades to assist in the preparation of multigroup data. Despite the variety and versatility of these methods, preparing accurate multigroup nuclear data still requires significant manual and computational effort as well as deep expertise.

Machine learning methods have been applied to numerous and diverse applications in nuclear science and engineering. A random forest model was used to choose the best group structure from a list generated by a simulated annealing algorithm for 1-D benchmark simulations [7]. An artificial neural network (ANN) was used to estimate time-dependent pressure and temperature responses to transient events in system level models of a nuclear reactor [8]. A Physics Informed Neural Network (PINN) was used to predict fuel temperature, peak cladding temperature, reactivity, and power in a loss of heat sink scenario for a nuclear battery [9]. ANNs have also outperformed conventional models when predicting nuclear binding energies [10]. A multilayer perceptron was able to predict nuclear cross section data for 7 different reactions more accurately than previous conventional methods [11].

Several machine learning methods have been applied to the generation of self-shielded nuclear data. In HTGR applications, ANNs have accurately predicted k-eigenvalues, reaction rates, and temperature coefficients using burnup and temperature data [12]. ANNs have been used to enhance the ultra fine group method by predicting self-shielded cross sections in the resonance region of the WIMS-69 structure, using fuel composition, temperature, and pin pitch [13] as inputs. Recent work [14] showed ANNs could be used to generate a shielded 56-group cross section library for 37 nuclides in PWR simulations. Training data were generated using the material and cross section processing module within the SCALE package [15], while principal component analysis was used to reduce the dimensionality of the inputs and outputs.

In the present work we focus on predicting shielding factors for 8-group nuclear cross sections with training data generated by neutron Monte Carlo simulations. Two ANNs were developed and trained on 8,500 continuous-energy OpenMC [16] pincell simulations. Each simulation had a unique fuel composition and included combinations of up to 90 nuclides. The networks were trained to predict total, fission, absorption, elastic and total scattering cross sections in the CASMO-8 energy group structure [16]. To confirm the models' performance their predictions were compared with a test set of 1,500 samples of reference cross sections unseen during training. The predicted and ground truth shielded cross sections in this test set agree to within 0.152% on average.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Training Data Generation

2.1.1. Simulation model parameters

10,000 OpenMC simulations of a light water reactor (LWR) pincell infinite lattice were used to generate 8,500 samples of training data, 1,500 of which were used in validation. An additional 1,500 unique samples of data were generated for testing. The geometry of the pincell is shown in Figure 1, and includes UOX fuel, zirconium cladding, a helium gap, and borated water coolant. The fuel, cladding, and coolant temperatures were set to 900K, 600K, and 562K, respectively. A 2-dimensional model was used, and reflective boundary conditions with 100% albedo were placed around the coolant. The simulations were run with 10 inactive and 90 active criticality cycles and 10,000 neutrons per cycle.

Figure 1. Pincell Geometry

2.1.2. Fuel composition definition

The isotopic composition of the fuel in each simulation was unique and selected using Latin hypercube sampling. The range of possible concentrations for each isotope used as a basis for Latin hypercube sampling was established using depletion simulations of UOX fuel pins in a LWR [17]. The fuel enrichment level of these simulations ranged from 1.6 to 19.9% a/o and were depleted from 18 to 210 MWd/kgIHM, depending on the enrichment. The upper and lower concentration limits of each nuclide were defined by finding its maximum and minimum concentrations across all depletion simulations, excluding zero concentrations in fresh fuel. 10% was then added or subtracted to the maximum and minimum concentrations found. This was done to ensure the training data covered the range of isotopic compositions expected in diverse UOX fueled LWR designs.

Although the depleted fuel compositions included 199 nuclides in total, these data were reduced to only the nuclides that were responsible for the greatest effect on the neutronics. These nuclides were identified according to their contribution to the one-group macroscopic total cross section and the total reaction rate of a material containing the maximum concentration of every nuclide. The blue curve in Figure 2 shows the cumulative sum of the material's macroscopic total cross section as nuclides are added in descending order of their individual macroscopic total cross sections. In this case, the 87 nuclides with the largest total cross sections contribute 99.9% of the material's total cross section. The total cross sections were calculated using one-group values taken from the raw ENDF data using OpenMC's data API. The one-group cross section was calculated by collapsing the raw data assuming a flat neutron flux. The orange curve in Figure 2 shows the cumulative sum of the material's total reaction rate as nuclides are added in descending order of their individual total reaction rates. Here the reaction rates were calculated using OpenMC tallies, and 86 nuclides with the largest total reaction rates contribute 99.9% of the material's total reaction rate. The intersection of these 87 and 86 nuclides produced 90 unique nuclides whose concentrations were chosen as input features for the neural networks.

Figure 2. Cumulative sum of macroscopic total cross sections (blue) and one group reaction rates normalized per unit starting particle (orange).

2.1.3. Data curation and feature engineering

The atomic concentrations of each nuclide in the fuel were used as input to the neural network. The total, absorption, fission, elastic scattering, and total scattering reaction rates and their uncertainties were tallied in the CASMO-8 group structure for each nuclide in all 10,000 samples. From these, the effective microscopic cross sections were calculated by dividing the reaction rate by the flux and atomic

concentration of each nuclide. The unshielded multigroup microscopic cross sections for each nuclide were calculated by collapsing cross sections obtained using OpenMC's data API to the CASMO-8 group structure using a flat neutron flux. The choice of weighting flux is arbitrary here since these unshielded cross sections are used as a baseline, from which the shielded data are computed as ratios. These ratios between the shielded and unshielded cross sections for 90 nuclides, 8 groups and 5 reactions then defined the high dimensional output space for the neural networks. To improve prediction accuracy and because only 18 of these nuclides were fissionable, two neural networks were trained: one for the 18 fissionable nuclides (FNN), and a second for the remaining nuclides (TNN).

2.2. Neural Network Architecture and Training Protocol

The two neural networks were implemented using the PyTorch library, where both networks used 90 neurons in their input layers, corresponding to the atomic concentrations of each nuclide. These concentrations [atm/b-cm] were scaled using SciPy's Standard scaler [18] before being used as inputs to the networks. The FNN was configured with 2 hidden layers containing 64 and 128 neurons. The output layer consisted of 144 neurons, corresponding to the 18 nuclides with fission cross sections in 8 groups. The TNN predicted the total, absorption, elastic scattering, and total scattering cross sections for all 90 nuclides in 8 groups. This network also had two hidden layers, with 128 and 512 neurons. The remaining parameters of the two networks were the same and are shown in Table I.

To prevent overfitting and optimize training time, early stopping was used along with a learning rate scheduler. The learning rate scheduler decreased the learning rate by a factor of 0.5 every 10 epochs if the validation loss did not achieve a new minimum. A patience counter was incremented each consecutive epoch the validation loss did not reach a new minimum. When the patience counter reached 250 the model stopped learning, but if a new minimum was reached then the counter was reset to 0.

Table I. Neural Network Parameters.

Parameter	Description
Activation Function	ReLU
Loss Function	Gaussian NLL ^a
Learning Rate	1.0×10^{-3}
Batch Size	300
FNN Topology	$90 \times 64 \times 128 \times 144$
TNN Topology	$90 \times 128 \times 512 \times 2880$

^a Gaussian Negative Log Likelihood Loss

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1. Quantitative Model Performance

A summary of the models' predictive accuracy is given in Table II. The table shows the training and test results from both models separately. The average quantities are weighted according to the number of output neurons in each network. It is important to note that the absolute error recorded represents the average absolute error of the entire training and test data sets in barns. These values are high due to several nuclides with cross section values in the millions of barns, but are included to contextualize the percentage error and loss values.

Table II. Neural Network Results on Test Data.

Metric	TNN	FNN	Average
Training Loss	0.00373	0.00717	0.00389
Training % Error	0.143%	0.235%	0.148%
Training Absolute Error [b]	15.74	28.24	16.37
Test Loss	0.00379	0.00722	0.00396
Test % Error	0.147%	0.246%	0.152%
Test Absolute Error [b]	16.21	23.09	16.55

Figures 3 and 4 show the predicted and ground truth shielded cross sections and unshielded cross sections from ENDF data for the test sample that yielded the least accurate predictions. Figure 3 (left) shows the predicted shielded total microscopic cross section for ^{238}U , as well as the ground truth cross section obtained from OpenMC tallies. The unshielded cross section from ENDF data is also shown for comparison. In all 8 energy groups the TNN's predictions are within 0.19 barns of the ground truth values at worst in absolute terms, and 0.7% in relative terms.

Figure 3 (right) shows the predicted fission microscopic cross section for ^{235}U , as well as the ground truth cross sections obtained from OpenMC tallies. In groups 5 and 6, corresponding to the energy region between 0.625 and 5530 eV, the shielded cross-sections increase relative to the unshielded cross-sections. This phenomenon occurs in materials containing certain combinations of nuclides and is a byproduct of choosing a uniform neutron spectrum for calculating the unshielded cross sections. The FNN can still capture this phenomenon accurately, predicting cross-sections within 4 barns and 2.5% of the ground truth values at worst in absolute and relative terms.

Figure 3 Predicted, ground truth, and unshielded total microscopic cross section for ^{238}U (left) and fission microscopic cross section for ^{235}U (right).

Figure 4 shows the predicted total microscopic cross sections for ^{240}Pu , as well as ground truth values and the unshielded cross sections, which had the worst overall results from the data set. The TNN predicted an absolute error of 695 barns and a percentage error of 18.6% in group 5 (0.625 to 4 eV). This point represents the resonance peak present in ^{240}Pu 's epithermal region where the ground truth value is around 3700 barns. The next highest error in Figure 4 was in group 4 (0.28 to 0.625 eV) with a percentage error of 1.8% and an absolute error of 3.4 barns. Despite this, on average the TNN's predictions for this sample specifically were within 55.89 barns and 0.49% of the ground truth values.

Figure 4 The predicted and ground truth total microscopic cross section for ^{240}Pu with the unshielded microscopic total cross section for comparison.

Figure 5 shows two histograms representing the prediction residuals, scaled to the OpenMC tally standard deviation of the corresponding ground truth value as well as the relative errors. The figure shows that the fraction of predictions within one, two, and three standard deviations of the ground truth were 91.37%, 97.12%, and 98.85%, respectively.

Figure 5. A histogram comparing the distribution of the test dataset relative errors with the standard deviation scaled residual errors from OpenMC simulations. This demonstrates the neural network accuracy is similar to the Monte Carlo residual error.

3.2. Impact of Training Data Size

Machine learning models frequently suffer from overfitting where the training loss is significantly lower than the validation or test loss [19]. A simple way to reduce overfitting is by increasing the number of samples used to train the model. Figure 6 shows the loss and percentage error for the training, validation, and test data sets as a function of the number of training samples used. We found that using 10,000 samples with a 70% training, 15% validation and 15% testing split gives losses of 0.00373, 0.00373 and 0.00396 in each data set respectively. The corresponding mean percent error values were 0.148%, 0.152%, and 0.152%.

Figure 6. Training curves showing the training, validation, and test loss (left) and mean percentage error (right) vs number of samples used to train the model.

4. CONCLUSION

Two Artificial Neural Network (ANN) models were trained to predict self-shielded microscopic cross sections in the fuel region of a light water reactor pincell model using nuclide concentrations as inputs. The data used in training these models were generated using tallies in the CASMO-8 group structure from OpenMC pincell simulations. The fuel composition in each simulation was a unique combination of 90 nuclides with concentrations ranging from 1.5 to 19.9 a/o and burnup levels from 18 to 210 MWd/kgIHM. The Fission Neural Network (FNN) was trained to predict fission cross sections, while the Total Neural Network (TNN) predicted the total, elastic scattering, capture and total scattering cross sections. The resulting models achieved a mean percentage error of 0.152%. An analysis of the distribution of residuals showed that 91.37% of predictions fell within one standard deviation of the corresponding OpenMC tally result. As shown in Figs. 4 to 6, 92.5% of predictions, even for the least accurate test case, were within 1% of the reference values. These results are consistent with the work of other groups [12,13,14], who each reported mean absolute percentage errors of less than 1% for group structures ranging from 4 to 56 groups and nuclide combinations of 29 to 295 in both pincell and lattice simulations. The success of these varied models suggests that the method scales effectively from simple, broad-group approximations to high-fidelity simulations with hundreds of tracked isotopes.

The most notable limitation observed in the models' performance was in predicting self-shielding of ^{240}Pu and ^{242}Pu . Prediction errors in these cases often exceeded 10% in energy groups 4 and 5 (0.28 to 4 eV). The ANNs developed in this work, however, were only manually optimized, and would benefit from a systematic optimization that could minimize the residuals in the plutonium predictions. Another simple way to mitigate this limitation would be to train neural networks specifically targeting plutonium nuclides and the problematic energy regions. Training data with increased coverage of problematic regions could also be generated. Although this type of post-hoc refinement is generally contrary to best practice in training ANNs, in this application the input space has fixed boundaries that are well-defined. Specifically, the input nuclide concentrations are constrained by the maximum and minimum concentrations found in a depletion calculation.

The present models are limited in their applicability to a specific geometry and temperature. Future work will expand the models' scope to include diverse reactor spectra, geometries and temperatures. These can be implemented using additional input neurons encoding temperature, spectrum, and geometry, or by training additional neural networks that can refine a basic infinite medium calculation. Simple ways to encode geometry have a basis in well-established methods such as the Wigner Rational Approximation for convex geometries. A deployable method also requires the ability to predict self-shielding in all nuclear data quantities for multigroup neutron transport including scattering matrices. The utility of the method also needs to be broadened by training neural network models to predict shielded quantities in a variety of commonly used group structures. Ultimately, the validity of the method must be determined by running multigroup simulations using the predicted shielded data and using data that were shielded using traditional methods. The accuracy of each simulation can then be compared with the equivalent continuous energy results enabling a simple and unambiguous evaluation of the method.

Data Availability

Codes and data used in this work are available upon request.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Dr. Valerio Mascolino for his helpful suggestions. This work was supported by DOE-NE award DE-NE009418.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. I. Bondarenko, et al. *Group Constants for Nuclear Reactor Calculations*. Consultants Bureau, New York, United States (1964).
- [2] A. H'ebert. "Application of Tone's and embedded self-shielding methods to pressurized water reactor assemblies." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 112**, pp. 439–449 (2018).
- [3] Y. Hou, Y. Wen, D. She, and L. Shi. "Comparison study on the subgroup method and the generalized Stamm'ler method for resonance self-shielding calculation." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 226**, p. 111824 (2026).
- [4] M. Sohail and M. H. Kim. "Estimation of self-shielded cross section by employing interference correction factors in subgroup method." *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, **volume 79**, pp. 150–157 (2015).
- [5] J. Rao, X. Peng, Q. Wu, Y. Yu, Q. Li, and K. Wang. "Relationship between Tone's method and embedded self-shielding method." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 166**, p. 108690 (2022).
- [6] R. MacFarlane and A. Kahler. "Methods for Processing ENDF/B-VII with NJOY." *Nuclear Data Sheets*, **volume 111**(12), pp. 2739–2890 (2010). Nuclear Reaction Data.
- [7] T. G. Saller, V. Nair, A. Till, and N. Gibson. "Using a Random Forest Model to Choose Optimized Group Structures." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 197**(8), pp. 2117–2135 (2023).
- [8] M. El-Sefy, A. Yosri, W. El-Dakhakhni, S. Nagasaki, and L. Wiebe. "Artificial neural network for predicting nuclear power plant dynamic behaviors." *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*, **volume 53**(10), pp. 3275–3285 (2021).
- [9] F. Antonello, J. Buongiorno, and E. Zio. "Physics informed neural networks for surrogate modeling of accidental scenarios in nuclear power plants." *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*, **volume 55**(9), pp. 3409–3416 (2023).
- [10] L.-X. Zeng, Y.-Y. Yin, X.-X. Dong, and L.-S. Geng. "Nuclear binding energies in artificial neural networks." *Phys Rev C*, **volume 109**, p. 034318 (2024).
- [11] S. Ili'c, N. Jovan'cevi'c, D. Kne'zevi'c, D. Maleti'c, C. Stieghorst, A. Nayak, S. Oberstedt, M. Hult, D. Boschmann, L. Kadri, Ozden, I. Arseni'c, and M. Krmar. "The use of artificial neural networks for the unfolding procedures in neutron activation measurements." *The European Physical Journal A*, **volume 61**(4), p. 80 (2025).
- [12] O. W. Calvin, Y. Che, Y. Wang, P. Balestra, and J. Ortensi. "Deployment of neural-network-based neutron microscopic cross sections in the Griffin reactor physics application." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 220**, pp. 111509 (2025).
- [13] S. Qin, Q. Zhang, J. Zhang, L. Liang, Q. Zhao, H. Wu, and L. Cao. "Application of deep neural network for generating resonance self-shielded cross-section." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 149**, p. 107785 (2020).
- [14] Y. M. Chan and J. Dufek. "A deep-learning representation of multi-group cross sections in lattice calculations." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 195**, pp. 110123 (2024).
- [15] Wieselquist, William A., Lefebvre, Robert Alexander, and Jessee, Matthew A., "SCALE Code System," (2020), <https://doi.org/10.2172/1616812>
- [16] P. K. Romano et al. "The OpenMC Monte Carlo particle transport code." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 82**, pp. 1–7 (2015).
- [17] J. Berry, P. Romano, and A. Osborne. "Upsampling Monte Carlo Reactor Simulation Tallies in Depleted Sodium-Cooled Fast Reactor Assemblies Using a Convolutional Neural Network." *Energies*, **volume 17**(9) (2024).
- [18] F. Pedregosa et al. "Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in Python." *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, **volume 12**, pp. 2825–2830 (2011).
- [19] J. Sietsma and R. J. Dow. "Creating artificial neural networks that generalize." *Neural Networks*, **volume 4**(1), pp. 67–79 (1991).